

Metal Chelate Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl Benzophenoneanil

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2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenoneanil (HMBA) is found to be a chelating agent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions. It gave a reddish brown bis-chelate (pH 10.0-10.8) with Cu^{2+} , a red bis-chelate (pH 9.0-9.8) with Ni^{2+} and a green bis-chelate (pH 10.8-11.5) with Co^{2+} . The composition of these chelates have been described on the basis of their elemental analysis. The complexes of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} were paramagnetic and the nickel complex was diamagnetic. Copper can be estimated gravimetrically.

THE reagents having -O-C = C-C = N- system have been investigated by several workers¹⁻⁵.

The present work deals with the preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenoneanil by the method suggested by G. Reddelien⁶ and its chelates with copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II). This reagent gives reddish brown precipitate with Cu^{2+} at pH 10.0 to 10.8 and red precipitate with Ni^{2+} at pH 9.0 to 9.8 and green precipitate with Co^{2+} at pH 10.8 to 11.5. The copper can be estimated gravimetrically from solution containing Cu^{2+} ions alone or in presence of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The compositions of these complexes have been discussed on the basis of their elemental analysis. The copper and cobalt complexes were found to be paramagnetic whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic. The quantitative estimation of copper was done.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenoneanil :

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone was prepared by Fries reaction of *p*-cresylbenzoate⁷. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (0.1), aniline (0.1 M) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) were heated at 160° for half an hour and then the temperature was raised to 180° for 5 min. It was cooled and the anil was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform was distilled out from the extract and the product was isolated.

It was crystallised from ethanol. Yellow crystals, m.p. 160°. Yield 70%. Found : C, 83.58; H, 5.90; N, 4.82. Calc for $(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO})$. C, 83.62; H, 5.92; N, 4.88%.

Preparation of metal complexes :

One percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

Copper complex : Cupric chloride solution (0.1 M, 10 ml) was diluted to 100 ml. and warmed upto

50°-60°. Excess of ammonium hydroxide was added till blue coloured solution is formed. A calculated volume of reagent solution was added with stirring followed with the addition of little excess of the reagent to ensure complete precipitation. The complex was digested on water bath for 10 min and filtered. It was washed with water till free from chloride ions, then with 10% ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. The chelate can be easily crystallised from benzene. The result of the estimation of copper from cupric chloride solution alone and in presence of Ni(II) and Co(II) are recorded in Table I. Found : Cu, 9.94; N, 4.38%. Calc. for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO})_2$. Cu, 9.99; N, 4.40%.

TABLE I—ESTIMATION OF Cu^{2+} IN THE SOLUTION OF Cu^{2+} ION ALONE AND IN PRESENCE OF Ni^{2+} OR Co^{2+} AT pH 10.8

Sr. No.	Wt. of the metal ion in mg.	Wt. of complex in mg.	Metal ion found in complex in mg.	Error in mg.
1.	Cu^{2+} 62.5	623.2	62.3	-0.2
2.	Cu^{2+} 62.5 Ni^{2+} 58.5	622.4	62.2	-0.3
3.	Cu^{2+} 62.5 Co^{2+} 58.4	623.4	62.3	-0.2

Nickel complex : Nickel complex was prepared by refluxing (1 hr) a requisite amount of reagent solution and nickel chloride solution (0.1 M) with ammonium hydroxide and ammonium acetate at pH 9.0-9.5 in alcoholic medium, when a red coloured complex was obtained. It was filtered out, washed with water till free from chloride ions and then with little ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. It can be crystallised easily from benzene. Found : Ni, 9.26; N, 4.38%. Calc. for $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO})_2$. Ni, 9.31; N, 4.43%.

Cobalt complex: It was prepared by refluxing (1 hr) a requisite amount of reagent solution with Co(II) chloride solution containing excess of ammonium hydroxide (pH 10.5–11.0) in alcoholic medium.

A green coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed with water till free from chloride ions and dried at 100°–110°. It can be crystallised from benzene. Found: Co, 9.28; N, 4.38%. Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO})_2$. Co, 9.34; N, 4.43%.

The quantitative estimation of nickel and cobalt was not possible.

All these metallic complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene and other organic solvents.

The molecular weight determined by cryoscopic method was in agreement with the empirical formula weight, showing that these chelates were monomers, represented by the general formula $\text{M}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO})_2$, where $M = \text{Cu}, \text{Ni}$ and Co .

The magnetic moments of the chelates were obtained by Guoy balance method. It was found that magnetic moment of copper complex was $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.74$

BM, and for cobalt complex $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.64$ BM at 36° corresponding to the presence of one unpaired electron in the Central metal ion whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic.

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